

ISic3321

Funerary inscription of Boulis

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object

Slab

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Autopsy

2013.10.02

Last Change

2017-02-04 - Jonathan Prag revised the EpiDoc, added text, translation, images, provenance

Place of origin (ancient)

Menae

Place of origin (modern)

Mineo

Provenance

Found in contrada Sparagagna and acquired by Orsi, 30 June 1903

Coordinates

37.28726, 14.66071

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 23255

Physical Description

A large quadrangular slab of sandstone, intact and finished on all sides, but left rough on the reverse

Dimensions

Height 64 cm

Width 75 cm

Depth 12 cm

Layout

One word on each of two lines, with clear space at the end of each line as well as above and below

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Very large clear letters without serifs, regularly cut: omicron is smaller and mid-line; epsilon middle bar is not joined to the vertical; alpha with straight bar; beta with closed eyes, the lower is larger.

Letter heights:

Lines 1-2: 170 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation not measured: mm

Text

1. Βοῦλι

2. χαῖρε

Apparatus

Manganaro: [ὁ δεῖνα Εὐ]βουλί-; Orsi [Εὐ]βουλί[δα]

Manganaro: [δα χρηστέ]χαῖρε

Translation (en)

Boulis, farewell!

Commentary

The name Βοῦλις is rare but attested at least 7 times across the Greek world according to LGPN s.v. Βοῦλις [<http://www.lgpn.ox.ac.uk/name/Βοῦλις>] , although not so far in Sicily. Consequently, the suggested expansion of the first line to the more common name Εὐβουλίδα, first proposed by Orsi, and subsequently by Manganaro, appears unnecessary - an assumption that finds support both in the fact that the stone is clearly intact and the text carefully laid out with space above, below and after the visible letters, and because the formula 'vocative + χαῖρε' is attested more than once in other epitaphs from Mineo.

Digital identifiers:

TM 645575

PHI 336159

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Photo J. Prag